

Literature review – LBW (Annex to D1.1)

Project full title	Innovative Al filler Wires for Aircraft Structure
Project acronym	IAWAS
Topic / Call	JTI-CS2-2017-CfP07-AIR-01-34
Grant Agreement no.	821371
Start Date	02/10/2018
Duration	03 months
Version number	01.0
Due date	31/12/2018
Submission Date	22/11/2018

DISSEMINATION LEVEL		
PU	Public	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	<input type="checkbox"/>
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	<input type="checkbox"/>
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	<input type="checkbox"/>

CHANGE CONTROL

Date	Version	Author (Company)	Changes to document
	v01.0	SONACA	Initial version
	V01.1		Inputs from XXX
	V01.2		Approved by Project Manager
	V01.3		Revised by Topic Manager

INDEX

CHANGE CONTROL.....	2
INDEX	3
ABBREVIATIONS	4
1. Scope.....	5
2. Base material – Al-Cu-Li Alloys.....	5
2.1 Al-Cu-Li Alloys introduction	5
2.1 Al-Cu-Li Alloys microstructure.....	6
3. Laser Beam Welding.....	8
3.1 LBW introduction.....	8
3.2 LBW – process parameters.....	9
4. LBW of Al-Cu-Li Alloys.....	11
4.1 Joint structure.....	11
4.2 Main known issues.....	13
4.2.1 Presence of high porosity in the weld:.....	13
4.2.2 Cracking:	15
4.2.2.1 Hot cracking	15
4.2.2.2 Liquation cracking:.....	17
4.2.3 Loss of mechanical properties.....	19
4.2.4 Corrosion.....	22
5. Applicability/Conclusions.....	23
6. REFERENCES	25

ABBREVIATIONS

IAWAS	Innovative Al filler Wires for Aircraft Structure
LBW	Laser Beam Welding
WAAM	Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing
TMP	Thermal-Mechanical Processing
HAZ	Heat Affected Zone
PMZ	Partially Melted Zone
FZ	Fusion Zone
EQZ	Non-dendritic Equiaxed grain Zone
CCZ	Columnar Crystal Zone
CDZ	Columnar Dendrite Zone
EDZ	Equiaxed Dendrite Zone
KoM	Kick-off Meeting

1. Scope

In the framework of the CleanSky project IAWAS, this report has been issued in order to support the deliverable “D1.1 – Suitable new aluminium alloys for wire manufacturing” aiming to define the specification for the new wire to be manufactured for Laser Beam Welding (LBW) and Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM) applications.

Other 3 reports will be delivered by UAC, Selectarc and Cranfield University, addressing respectively alloy casting and extruding, drawing wire, and WAAM. All together with the feedbacks from the first LBW and WAAM test results will allow the completion of D1.1.

The parallel goal of this written review is to provide an overall view of the current status of the LBW technology applied to age-hardening Al-Cu-Li alloys. It will serve as a starting point, to outline the different ways to improve the quality of LBW parts made of Al-Cu-Li. Firstly, the alloys to be welded are briefly described in order to understand their microstructure and their behaviour when subjected to a fusion welding process. Afterwards, LBW advantages and main process parameters are quickly presented. Section 4 is focussed on LBW of Al-Cu-Li alloys, encountered problems and expertise are presented. Finally, a discussion about the application of this review to the development of new filler wires to obtain the highest quality of the joint is made in Section 5.

2. Base material – Al-Cu-Li Alloys

2.1 Al-Cu-Li Alloys introduction

The reasons for aluminium alloys to become one of the major materials used in civilian aircraft construction are its low density combined to high mechanical properties and its good corrosion resistance.

The continuous quest to save weight, to enhance performance, and to reduce inspection and maintenance burden, has led to the development of the Al-Li alloys, currently in their third generation. This last generation has been developed by optimizing alloy composition and thermal-mechanical processing (TMP) for a good balance of the following features [21]:

- Density
- Strength and toughness balance with low anisotropy of mechanical properties
- Fatigue crack growth resistance
- Corrosion resistance
- Thermal stability
- Manufacturability

Lithium, the lightest metal on Earth, is the primary reason of their proper properties. It has been proved that the addition of 1 wt % provides approximately 3% decrease in density, 6% increase in Young’s elastic modulus, it enables the formation of efficient hardening precipitates and it imparts higher fatigue crack growth resistance [15] [21].

Their main technical drawback is the Lithium’s high reactivity and low evaporation temperature. Due to these properties, most of their products need to be cold manufactured, being the reason why the LBW of this alloys represent a challenge still not perfectly solved yet. Besides, some security constraints are tied to this element, increasing even more the processing cost and feasibility [14] [13].

2.1 Al-Cu-Li Alloys microstructure

For these alloys, the microstructure, the composition, and the homogeneity are of outmost importance to obtain a high quality product [21] [23]. Therefore, their understanding is crucial to succeed.

One of the first steps of IAWAS is the selection of the material to be welded. Two alloys have been proposed, 2198 and 2060. They will be through-welded in a first campaign on flat sheets. The candidate showing the best weldability with the specific technology (conventional LBW) to be used will be identified. The composition of these alloys can be seen in next figure:

	Li	Cu	Mg	Ag	Zr	Sc	Mn	Zn
2198	1.0	3.2	0.5	0.4	0.11	-	0.5 max	0.35 max
2060	0.75	3.95	0.85	0.25	0.11	-	0.3	0.4

Figure 1 Composition of alloys to be tested in IAWAS

Properties achieved in T8 condition, after a solution treatment, quenching and artificial aging, make this condition the preferred one for structural applications. In T8, the phases contributing to strengthen the alloy are mostly: T_1 (Al_2CuLi), θ' -type (Al_2Cu), δ' (Al_3Li) and δ'/β' (Al_3Li/Al_3Zr), being T_1 the most efficient of them with platelet shape aligned on $\{111\}$ Al matrix planes. The thin, high aspect ratio T_1 plates are found uniformly distributed within the grains. In comparison with the localized slip mechanisms in other Al-Li alloys, the T_1 precipitate acts as non-shearable barrier to promote homogeneous deformation, resulting in the increased strength and fracture toughness of alloys [2].

Figure 2 TEM bright-field image-2060T8 alloy. Arrows indicating two variants of primary strengthening T_1 phase

θ' -type precipitates are thought to be isomorphous and isostructural with θ' precipitates in the Al-Cu system, once Li is added, it is suggested that the Li atoms could be added in substitution form into the defect sites [21].

The main alloying additions of 3rd-generation alloys controlling these phases, and therefore their properties, are the following [21] [11] [10]:

- Li: Added for density reduction and strengthening via solid-solution and precipitation. It participates in the formation of T_1 , $T_2(Al_6CuLi_3)$ and θ' -type precipitates. It is also presented in δ' (Al_3Li) precipitates helping to strengthen the alloy. It is apparent that the balance between T_1 and δ' is controlled by the Cu:Li ratio. For alloys with a high Cu:Li ratio, the T_1 precipitation is predominant. Conversely, in alloys with a low Cu:Li ratio, δ' will be readily observed.

- Mg: Added for density reduction and strengthening via solid-solution and precipitation. It can be a substitute for Li in the T_1 precipitate. It is proposed that Mg and Ag lead to the formation of Ω precipitates $Al_2(Cu-Ag, Li-Mg)$, isomorphous and isostructural with T_1 [10] [11] [21].
- Cu: Added to form the main strengthening precipitates: T_1 and θ' -type. It also combines with Li to form the T_2 phase (Al_6CuLi_3), which can increase the toughness [9]. T_1 can heterogeneously nucleate on subgrain boundaries and dislocations and the T_1 and T_2 phases can form at the grain boundaries, although too much grain boundary precipitation can be detrimental to toughness as it will be presented in Section 4.
- Ag: Added for solid-solution and precipitation strengthening. Ag enhances the nucleation of Ω precipitates, especially in the presence of magnesium. It also increases the aging kinetics and peak strength, but adds significant raw material costs.
- Zn: Added for solid-solution strengthening and corrosion improvement.
- Zr: Added for control of recrystallization and texture. It forms the coherent β' (Al_3Zr) dispersoid. The δ' phase also precipitates epitaxially on the surface of Al_3Zr dispersoids.
- Mn: Its additions form incoherent $Al_{20}Cu_2Mn_3$ dispersoids, which helps decreasing recrystallization, controlling grain size, and controlling texture evolution during thermo-mechanical processing (ex. extrusion) [11]. Additionally, they have been shown to homogenize slip and thereby improve damage tolerance with regards to fracture toughness and fatigue. It should be noted that in work [12] it was showed that Li can also be present in Mn dispersoids.
- Ti: Added as a grain refiner during solidification of ingots
- Na and K: Considered as impurities affecting fracture toughness
- Sc: Added to improve the strength (via solid solution, precipitation and grain structure control) while enhancing weldability. It is well known that Sc readily combines with Zr to form a highly effective and complex $Al_3(Zr_xSc_{1-x})$ dispersoid. [25].
- Fe and Si: Considered as impurities affecting fracture toughness, fatigue, and corrosion. In the presence of Cu, Fe forms an insoluble constituent phase (Al_7Cu_2Fe) that needs to be minimised.

Microstructure is not only determined by the composition of the alloy, but also by its thermo-mechanical history that plays an important role, as it has already been demonstrated. For example, T_1 phase is strongly affected by cold deformation (stretching, cold rolling, and cold compressing) prior to aging, increasing the number of T_1 precipitates by approximately two orders of magnitude but reducing the precipitation of T_1 and T_2 at grain boundaries. The result of these two effects is a highly beneficial contribution to in the strength and fracture toughness. [21] [11]

Figure 1 contains a scheme showing the phases described here above for a 2099 and 2199 alloy, it can be applied to both alloys (2060 and 2198) to be considered in IAWAS:

Figure 3 Precipitates and dispersoids that contribute to strength and toughness in 2099 and 2199 alloys [11]

3. Laser Beam Welding

3.1 LBW introduction

In the aircraft industry, the development of a joining method applicable to age-hardening Al–Cu–Li alloys offers the possibility to replace a very laborious and ineffective technology of riveting. The achievement of a junction keeping these base material properties will lead to important time, cost and weight savings leading also to lower fuel consumptions [16] [17].

The main fusion welding processes are: gas welding, arc welding and high energy welding. LBW belongs to the high energy beam welding, and it has been considered as one the most promising routes for this mechanical joining substitution. One of its interests resides in the ratio between heat input and power density shown in the following graphic:

Figure 4 Heat input – power density for fusion welding processes [27]

Up to 20% weight saving can be expected with LBW of these innovative alloys instead of the current riveting solution for a typical aircraft (Figure 5). Indeed, this technology presents appealing characteristics outlined below:

- The reduction of the needed material compared to riveting. It is related to the overlap joint required by riveting [24].

Figure 5 Riveting VS LBW [22] [19]

- Compared to other welding methods, it brings a high-energy concentration and a moderate size of the heated spot, which makes it possible to obtain joints where the welding bath has a relatively small volume. Thus, the welding can be focused on small areas or on those not easily accessible.
- High-speed laser welding allows approximately a tenfold reduction of specific energy expenses compared to conventional electric arc methods. The heat-affected zone, and, as a consequence, the deformation of parts is minimised.
- It provides high productivity, high weld quality, low distortion manufacturing flexibility and ease of automation [16] [17].
- It can be easily automated with robotic machinery for large volume production.
- No electrode is required.
- It can be welded through shielding gas and no vacuum is required.
- It does not produce any X-Rays.
- It is a non-contact process, therefore, it does not involve wear.
- It produces weld aspect ratio (i.e. depth to width ratio) of 10:1.
- Wide variety of materials can be welded, including aluminium alloys, and it has the ability to weld metals with dissimilar physical properties.

For larger metallic aircraft LBW with 6000 alloys (weldable aluminium alloys) has already shown advantages [24]. For small models the smaller panel sizes provide some shorter weld seam, which represents another challenge to be taken into account.

3.2 LBW – process parameters

LBW is a process that melts and joins metals by heating them with a laser beam. The laser beam can be focused and directed by optical means to achieve high power densities. The laser selected for this project is a solid-state laser, a Nd-YAG laser of a power of 3kW (continuous mode).

Figure 6 Laser beam welding process

One of the problems of Al alloys laser beam welding is its high reflectivity. As much as about 95% of can be reflected by a polished metal surface. Reflectivity is slightly lower with a Nd-YAG laser beam, the technology to be used in IAWAS or with a fibre laser. Surface modifications such as roughening, oxidizing, and coating can significantly reduce reflectivity, if this problem is detected these surface modifications can be adopted. Once a keyhole is established, absorption is high because the beam is trapped inside this hole by internal reflection [27].

A shielding Gas is compulsory to properly weld metals such as aluminium alloys. This constraint is due to the creation of a plasma (an ionic gas) during LBW, due to ionization by the laser beam. The plasma can absorb and scatter the laser beam and significantly reduce the depth of penetration. Helium is often preferred to argon as the shielding gas for high-power LBW because of greater penetration depth [27].

There are different variants of laser welding technologies already developed, like for example hybrid laser welding GMAW (Figure 7), in which the energy coming from the laser is assisted by other technologies (such as MIG for example).

Figure 7 CRM Laser – GMAW Hybrid

Nevertheless, it was agreed in the IAWAS KoM to focus the efforts of this project on conventional LBW. The main parameters to be taken into account are:

- Laser power (W): low laser power might lead to a lack of penetration. Weld width and depth increase with the increase of laser power when the welding speed is constant but a very high power can produce other problems such as corrosion or vaporizing of light elements.

Figure 8 Lack of penetration [7]

- Welding speed (m/min): In [7] it was stated that weld depth and width decreased exponentially with a decrease in speed, indicating a transition in the mechanism from deep penetration to conduction weld. Only few pores were observed on the weld/base material interface, and the degree of porosity of the laser weld was observed to be unaffected by the depth of penetration. High speeds will produce a large gradient in the joint and generate with it hot cracking problems.
- Heat input (KJ/m): Moderate heat input leads to high quality weld bead with full penetration, no cracks, and less oxidation [7]. High welding temperatures will also produce a large gradient in the joint and therefore hot cracking problems.

- Shielding gas to protect the molten pool method: we can influence the results by changing the gas, the way to project it and its flow rate (L/min)
- Focus position.
- Welding direction (push or pull).

For each filler wire to be tested, a pre-test campaign will be carried out to optimise these parameters.

Even if it is not the goal of IAWAS, it shall be noted that the use of other LBW variants is very promising. For example the use of a hybrid laser GMAW combining the highly focused intensity of a laser with the joint filling capability of the traditional MIG process, leads to narrower treated zone and should limit the vaporizing.

4. LBW of Al-Cu-Li Alloys

4.1 Joint structure

The structure formed by Laser welded aluminium alloy joint consists of the different areas presented below and in Figure 9 [3]:

- Heat affected zone (HAZ).
- Partially melted zone (PMZ).
- Fusion zone (FZ):
 - Non-dendritic equiaxed grain zone (EQZ).
 - Columnar dendrite zone (CDZ).
 - Equiaxed dendrite zone (EDZ).

After welding, the variation of grain structure in fusion zone is related to the reached temperature and the rate of cooling. Within FZ, solute segregation occurs due to non-equilibrium solidification. For an Al-Cu-Li alloys welded without filler wire, most precipitates that are initially present in the base alloy dissolve during the welding process. During solidification, segregation occurs, taking most of the Cu to the grain boundaries and producing the depletion of this element in grain interiors. The result is a grain boundary with a concentration near eutectic and α -Al matrix grains without most of the alloying elements. Consequently, FZ contains a decreased quantity of δ' (Al₃Li), θ' (Al₂Cu) and T₁ (Al₂CuLi) phases precipitates [3]. The mechanical properties and corrosion resistance due to this structure are to be avoided (See section 4.2-Main known issues).

In particular, and as showed in Figure 9, EQZ forms in a narrow molten region between PMZ and CDZ. Fine equiaxed grains surrounded by grain boundary eutectic constituents weaken the EQZ and lead to poor mechanical and corrosion properties. Constituents and proportion of eutectic phases on grain boundaries also show intimate connection with the tensile properties and the hot cracking of T-joints. It can be concluded that this zone is an important region that requires great attention, the use of a filler material to perform the welding and the control of its composition and microstructure is compulsory to improve the weld quality [6].

Figure 9 Beam structure of a laser beam welded 2A97-T3 Al-Cu-Li alloy (Barker's reagent) [3]

4.2 Main known issues

As with other aluminium alloys, there are several weldability issues associated with this new material. The main issues are porosity, hot cracking, and loss of mechanical properties. They were announced in the IAWAS proposal [19] and they are further explained in the present document. Corrosion and liquation cracking issues are also reported in this list.

4.2.1 Presence of high porosity in the weld:

The high presence of porosity in the weld is a usual issue in the welding of Al alloys and especially Li-containing Al alloys (Figure 10 and Figure 11).

Figure 10: Weld seam between 1.6 mm-thick AA2198 sheets performed by laser beam welding with AA4047 filler wire [17]

Figure 11 Morphology of the porosity formed in LB-welded joint of 2060 Al-Cu-Li alloy [7]

In terms of size, shape, and location, porosity can be described as interdendritic porosity or bulk porosity. Interdendritic porosity occurs when gas bubbles are formed or entrapped between dendrite arms in the solidification substructure, whereas bulk porosity is associated to the spherical pores that result from supersaturation of gases in the weld pool [26].

The high presence of porosity in the weld induces a loss of mechanical properties and can be related to several causes:

- The vaporizing of low melting point alloying elements like Li and Mg [16] [17] [18].
- The vaporizing of organic contaminant located on the surface of the filler wire and/or the parts to be joined [8].
- The entrapment of the environmental or shielding gas used during welding [18].
- The hydrogen contamination that can lead to interdendritic microporosity [16].
- The presence of humidity.
- The high Li reactivity.

The solubility of gases (mainly applicable to H) rapidly decreases with the decrease of temperature during the solidification process. The addition of alloying elements might influence this solubility, for example, Cu and Si additions decrease the H solubility, and then increase porosity; Mg additions have the contrary effect [26]. Besides, the large thermal conduction of Al alloy results in

rapid cooling rate of the molten pool. When the escape speed of the bubbles is smaller than the solidifying speed of the molten pool, porosities will be formed [7]. In addition, the natural formation of an alumina coating can also block their way out. To avoid this last effect, the use of a shielding gas is useful.

Figure 12 Bubble of gas entrapped. Solidifying speed quicker than bubble speed [1]

Operating parameters can also affect the porosity: signal form, the position and configuration of the welding or the bad quality of the gas shielding [1]. In [7] the influence of the laser power is demonstrated. In that study, with the increase of this parameter, porosity ratio increases at first, and then declines, and then increases again. Thus, few or even no porosity is generated under adequate-moderate heat input. In the same article it is demonstrated how important is the cooling rate, thanks to a lower cooling rate less porosity was obtained with thicker plate, which opposes the general believing.

Development paths:

The following points shall be taken into account to prevent the presence of porosity in the weld:

- Ensuring the cleanliness of the surface of the filler wire and the parts to be welded through a meticulous surface cleaning (degreasing followed by chemical pickling) in order to avoid any organic contaminants. To guaranty a proper storage of the materials is compulsory.
- Due to the Li high reactivity, the use of a shielding gas is important. Nevertheless, flow rate shall be controlled.
- Limiting the content of low melting point alloying element in the composition of the Al filler wire [16] [17] [18].
- Controlling the hygrometry and the temperature of the welding cell [1]
- The porosity ratio is closely related to the welding parameters, especially the welding power [7].
- Lowering the cooling rate so that the bubbles have more time to escape for example by post-heating the material.
- Controlling the whole of the beam body

4.2.2 Cracking:

4.2.2.1 Hot cracking

Due to their high thermal expansion coefficient Al-Li alloys are very sensitive to hot cracking, also known as solidification cracking. It is one of the major defects that can occur during metal solidification. It is the result of an inadequate melt feeding and/or a large solidification interval of the alloy that initiate micro-pores and severe deformation during the metal solidification leading to the opening and propagation of cracks [16]. Figure 13 gives typical SEM micrographs of hot cracking in autogenous welded Li-containing Al alloys.

The location for this cracking can be the weld centreline or anywhere in the weld and HAZ. Solidification cracks usually occur towards the end of solidification, when the cumulative effect of restraint builds up to a maximum and the solid contacts between neighbouring dendrites are not strong enough to withstand the contraction stresses [26].

Figure 13: SEM micrographs illustrating typical hot cracking in autogenous welded Li-containing Al alloys: (a) AA8090 and (b) AA2195 [17]

If the compositions are adjusted, the elements responsible for cracking can be kept to their minimum and cracking problems could be solved. Weldalite 2195 alloy was developed in this way [27], the levels of copper and lithium were kept in the minimum. Strength sacrifice by reduction in these elements was compensated by the addition of silver. This alloy has proven to be weldable by all welding processes and is reported to be free from hot cracking [27].

Development paths: The paths of improvement for preventing the hot cracking phenomena are:

- Modification of the liquid composition through the filler material in order to reduce the solidification interval (i.e. addition of Si) and modify the microstructure of the weld from coarse or directional solidified grain structures with potential segregations to microstructures that are much less sensitive to hot cracking, such as fine equiaxed grain structures (i.e. through addition of Zr or Sc) or fine microstructures containing eutectic forming compounds (i.e. through addition of Si) [16] [20]
- Modification of the laser process (i.e. two laser sources of less energy) in order to create a fine equiaxed grain region in the weld, less sensitive to hot cracking [16].
- Post-heating the area to be welded in order to reduce the solidification rate [20].
- Decrease Li.
- Cu seems to have a direct influence in hot cracking sensibility. Its quantity needs to be optimised.
- Addition of Ag.

In reference [6] a new type wire CW3 (Al-6.2Cu-5.4Si) was investigated for the welding of 2060-T8/2099-T83 alloys. This wire was specially developed aiming to solve the hot cracking issue. Results were compared to the ones obtained with conventional wire AA4047 (Al-12Si). Main modifications in CW3 composition are the addition of Cu and small quantities of Mn and Ti, and the reduction of Si. Improvements were noticed in intergranular strength, hot cracking susceptibility and tensile properties. Typical non-dendritic equiaxed zone (EQZ) was observed along welds' fusion boundary. Hot cracks and fractures during the load were always located within the EQZ, however, it could be restrained by CW3. T2 phase by CW3 also resulted in microscopic intergranular reinforcement and improvement of macroscopic tensile properties. In addition, bridging caused by richer substructure dendrites within CW3 weld's columnar zone resulted in much lower hot cracking susceptibility of the whole weld. No negative effect on porosity was observed. Improvements regarding cracking and porosity compared to conventional 4047 filler wire can be noticed in Figure 14.

Figure 14 Optical macrographs showing the difference on the outer appearance of the weld: cracks are observed using AA4047 wire (a) and crack-free weld obtained with CW3 wire (b).

4.2.2.2 Liquation cracking:

During aluminum alloy welding the base metal immediately adjacent to the fusion boundary is heated to a temperature between the liquidus and the eutectic temperatures. This results in melting of the base metal eutectic and formation of a partially melted zone (PMZ) within the HAZ. The presence of substantial amounts of eutectic at the grain boundaries in the PMZ can cause post-weld embrittlement. [26]

Figure 15 Phase diagram Al-Li

Since the PMZ is weakened by grain boundary liquation, it cracks when the solidifying weld metal contracts and pulls it. Most aluminum alloys are susceptible to liquation cracking [27]. As the Al-Li eutectic has a higher formation temperature than the Al-Cu eutectic (548°C), the problem is slightly minimised.

Figure 16 PMZ cracking in 2219 aluminium welded with filler metal 1100 [27]

Figure 17 Liquation cracking mechanism

The severity of grain boundary melting and the thermal stresses causing cracking can be reduced by decreasing the power input, which is why lower power input processes are preferred for welding high-strength aluminium alloys.

4.2.3 Loss of mechanical properties

The welding process induces the dissolution of the strengthening phases and the vaporizing of some alloying elements needed for these phases to be formed (i.e. Li, Mg) leading to a local loss of mechanical strength of the base material at the weld location.

In [2] 2060-T8 alloy was welded with 5087 Al-Mg filler wire, Figure 18 shows the micro-hardness variations across the joint and the tensile properties of the base material and the welded one. The average hardness of the fusion zone is nearly half that of the base metal. The joint tensile strength is about 63% of that of the base metal and the elongation is also reduced.

Specimen	Orientation	Ultimate tensile strength (MPa)	Yield strength (MPa)	Elongation (%)
Base metal	LR	499	428	14.3
AA2060-T8	LT	498	414	14.0
As-welded joint	Transverse	317	235	1.6

LR – parallel to the rolling direction; LT – normal direction.

Figure 18 Joint properties – 2060-T8 alloy welded with 5087 Al-Mg filler wire

All tensile fractures occur within the fusion zone. Figure 19 shows the side-view fracture surface morphology, which is microscopically rough associated to the grain morphology exposed. The cracking propagation mode is intergranular. This tendency is facilitated as a result of alloying element segregation or intergranular coarse phases, which leads to weakening grain boundary. The coarse grain-boundary phases are in favour of stress concentration and thus, the nucleation of micro-voids is promoted due to the localized deformation. The micro-voids coalesce and cracks promptly propagate through the paths of less resistance before the ultimate failure occurs [2].

Figure 19 side-view fracture surface morphology

Development paths:

The main solutions for preventing this loss of mechanical strength are:

- The use of filler wire containing elements like Zr, Sc or Cr that will promote fine equiaxed grain microstructures [16] [20]. The addition of scandium in combination with Zirconium increases the specific strength and stiffness of aluminium alloys. In [25] its additions accounted for an exceptional strength and improved recrystallization resistance. The addition of Zr modifies the Sc-dispersoids by both refining their size and increasing their thermal stability. In this study, recrystallization was fully inhibited for the alloys containing both Sc and Zr.
- Adjustment of the laser process in order to limit the heat affected zone and promote fine equiaxed grain microstructures [16]. The larger heat input causes the lower micro-hardness distribution of the corresponding joint. This parameter needs to be controlled to obtain appropriate properties [7]
- Through heat treatments. The study in reference [23] clearly shows how the heat treatment of the welded joint can help to restore the bead proper microstructure (Figure 20) leading to good mechanical properties (Figure 22). After welding, the best proposed combination of treatments is solution heat treatment, quenching and artificial ageing [23]. It makes the joint strength appreciably greater but decreases the strength of the base alloy outside the heat affected zone of the welding process yielding a welded joint strength equal to 0.85 of the strength of the base alloy in the received condition (quenching + artificial ageing).

Figure 20 Bead microstructure. Magnification x10 or x100.

Figure 21 Micro-hardness; 1—welding + annealing; 2— welding + annealing + quenching; 3— welding + annealing + quenching + ageing; 4— welding [23]

Figure 22 Stress σ versus the strain; 1—sample without heat treatment; 2—sample after quenching; 3—sample after quenching and ageing; 4— sample after annealing, quenching, and ageing [23]

4.2.4 Corrosion

For Al-Cu-Li alloys, the presence of lithium may increase the corrosion susceptibility. As well, the modified microstructure after welding may create areas of different electrochemical potentials prone to galvanic corrosion.

In reference [3], the microstructure and corrosion behaviour of laser beam welded 2A97 alloy were investigated. It was demonstrated that the segregation of alloying elements within the fusion zone produces a non-uniform distribution of precipitates across the weld. It made the weld susceptible to localized corrosion, which initially occurs at high angle grain boundaries where a high population density of T_1 phase precipitates is present and, subsequently, develops into grain interior through preferential dissolution of T_1 phase precipitates. It was reported that, in NaCl solution, corrosion initiates at interdendritic intermetallic with selective dissolution of Al and Li, resulting in a copper-rich remnant, which subsequently acts as effective cathode supporting the dissolution of alloy matrix.

Besides, since the various weld zones are subjected to different degrees of heating and cooling rates, the distribution of the precipitates in the various weld zones may be significantly different. Consequently, their corrosion behaviour may be significantly different too.

In reference [4], LBW of AA6061 base alloy with AA4043 filler wire was analysed. Galvanic corrosion occurs in the weld, with fusion zone and base alloy being the cathode and anode respectively.

Development paths:

From these different investigations we can conclude that we need to control not only the corrosion compatibility between the wire and the base material but also the balance between the electrochemical potential of the different phases constituting the microstructure in the bead.

Two ways may lead to a good corrosion performance:

- Working with a wire with similar composition as the base material, the performance of a TMP will be needed to restore the microstructure, and therefore, to avoid the creation of a galvanic cell.
- If an alloy less susceptible to the latest problem is used. It will be necessary to make sure that the galvanic cell is not established between the base material and the bead.

As other hint to follow, it has been demonstrated that a small addition Zn (0.72%) stimulates the precipitation of T_1 phase. In this way, strength and corrosion resistance are improved. The combination of Mg and Zn (with an Mg/Zn ratio less than one) has also shown the same influence having a great impact on corrosion [5].

Processing parameters are also to be controlled to avoid corrosion. Ref [7] shows how corrosion is produced by increasing the heat input. Thus, it needs to be moderate.

5. Applicability/Conclusions

The challenges for laser beam welding of Al-Cu-Li alloys are to provide crack free joints with low porosity, resulting in high mechanical performance of the welded joint, as close as possible from the base material.

The focus of IAWAS project will be on the development of filler wires, however it won't be enough to obtain a high weld quality if parallel work is not done on the optimisation of the process parameters and conditions. Indeed, heat input, welding speed and laser power will determine the cooling rate and influence the final microstructure. Cooling rate needs to be optimised (lowering it) to avoid porosity and hot cracking. Besides, the cleanliness of the material (filler wire and base material) and a careful surface preparation are of outmost importance. A shielding gas is needed for protecting the melted material, it shall be projected with the required angle, flow and speed not to introduce porosity. Preheating the area to be welded in order to reduce the solidification rate is believed to be beneficial.

Final properties can also be improved with a post-TMP, but depending on the final application, it would not always be feasible. For Al-Cu-Li alloy base material, solution heat treatment, quenching and artificial aging is beneficial to recover and to homogenise the mechanical properties and to avoid corrosion issues. Nevertheless, introduction of a new step in the process (thermal treatment or cold deformation) will increase process complexity, cost and leading time.

The use of a filler wire is compulsory to obtain high mechanical properties if a TMP is not possible after welding. Regarding filler wire composition, one specific study showed very good results using CW3 (Al-6.2Cu-5.4Si-0.32Mn-0.16Ti) [6]. Base on the review of all the information, the recommended elements to use in the next composition are the following:

- Si that is effective to reduce the solidification interval preventing porosity and hot cracking. Wire with around 5.5% showed the best results [6].
- Cu that takes part in the T_2 , T_1 and θ' -type precipitates conferring high mechanical properties. Around 6% additions were found satisfactory [6].
- Ag can be beneficial to harden the weld without inducing hot cracking.
- Mn forms incoherent dispersoids which help to decrease crystallization and control grain size, the same as Ti [6].
- The addition of Zr, Sc and Cr needs to be investigated, as these elements shall promote fine equiaxed grain structures having a good influence on its properties [25].
- It has been demonstrated that a small addition Zn (0.72%) stimulates the precipitation of T_1 phase. In this way, strength and corrosion resistance are improved. Whereas, the high Mg filler is proven to be not appropriate [2], the combination of Mg and Zn (with an Mg/Zn ratio less than one) seems to have great impact on corrosion [5].
- Limiting the content of low melting point alloying element will reduce the risk of porosity (i.e. Li).

Precipitates play a very important role, acting as obstacles to dislocation motion and hence improving strength. In order to obtain the optimal mechanical properties, the distribution of the precipitates has to be carefully controlled, in terms of size, volume fraction and inter-particle spacing [25]. Elements producing or keeping such precipitates will be beneficial.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] MASTRANGELO Olivier; Présentation : Soudage des alliages d'aluminium ; Institut de Soudure ; Journée technique 7 novembre 2018
- [2] Xinyi Zhang, Wuxiong Yang, Rongshi Xiao; Microstructure and mechanical properties of laser beam welded Al–Li alloy 2060 with Al–Mg filler wire; High-power and Ultrafast Laser Manufacturing Lab, Institute of Laser Engineering, Beijing University of Technology, Beijing 100124, China 2015
- [3] Xinxin Zhanga, Bing Liua, Xiaorong Zhoua, Junjie Wang, Teruo Hashimotoa, Chen Luob, Zhihua Sunb, Zhihui Tangb, Feng Lub; Laser welding introduced segregation and its influence on the corrosion behaviour of Al–Cu–Li alloy; Corrosion Science 135 (2018) 177–191
- [4] A.B.M. Mujibur Rahman a, 1, S. Kumar a, A.R. Gerson; Galvanic corrosion of laser weldments of AA6061 aluminium alloy; Corrosion Science Volume 49, Issue 12, December 2007, Pages 4339–4351
- [5] Mechanical Property and Intergranular Corrosion Sensitivity of Zn-Free and Zn-Microalloyed Al-2.7Cu-1.7Li-0.3Mg Alloys
- [6] Bing Han, Wang Tao, Yanbin Chen, Hao Li; Double-sided laser beam welded T-joints for aluminum-lithium alloy aircraft fuselage panels: Effects of filler elements on microstructure and mechanical properties; Optics and Laser Technology
- [7] Cheng Gu & Yanhong Wei & Xiaohong Zhan & Dan Zhang & Shuai Ren & Hongbing Liu & Hao Li; Investigation of welding parameters on microstructure and mechanical properties of laser beam-welded joint of 2060 Al–Cu–Li alloy; 2016
- [8] Kazanas P., Deherkar P., Almeida P., Lockett H. and Williams S. (2012), "Fabrication of geometrical features using wire and arc additive manufacture, Proc IMechE Part B: J Engineering Manufacture, DOI: 10.1177/ 0954405412437126.
- [9] W. A. Cassada and G. J. Shiflet, "The influence of high plastic strain on precipitation from solid solution in third generation Al–Li alloys," Mater. Sci. Forum, vol. 794–796, pp. 1020–1025, 2014.
- [10] N. Brodusch, M. Trudeau, P. Michaud, L. Rodrigue, J. Boselli, and R. Gauvin, "Contribution of a new generation field-emission scanning microscope in the understanding of a 2099 Al–Li alloy," Microsc. Microanal., vol. 18, pp. 1393–1409, 2012.
- [11] C. Giummarra, B. Thomas, and R. J. Rioja, "New aluminum lithium alloys for aerospace applications," in Proceedings of the Light Metals Technology Conference, 2007.
- [12] Y. Ma, X. Zhou, G. E. Thompson, T. Hashimoto, P. Thomson, and M. Fowles, "Distribution of intermetallics in an AA 2099-T8 aluminium alloy extrusion," Mater. Chem. Phys., vol. 126, no. 1–2, pp. 46–53, Mar. 2011.
- [13] Javier Otero, Aleaciones metálicas en aplicaciones aeronáuticas, The university of Edinburgh August 2015
- [14] Dirk Dittrich*, Jens Standfuss, Jens Liebscher, Berndt Brenner, Eckhard Beyer, Laser Beam Welding of Hard to Weld Al Alloys for a Regional Aircraft Fuselage Design – First Results, Fraunhofer IWS Dresden, Winterbergstrasse 28, 01277 Dresden, Germany

- [15] K. K. Sankaran and N. J. Grant, 'The structure and properties of splat-quenched aluminum alloy 2024 containing lithium additions', vol. 44, no. 2, pp. 213–217, 1980
- [16] Cao X., Wallace W., Poon C. and Immarigeon (2003), Research and Progress in Laser Welding of Wrought Aluminum Alloys.I. Laser Welding Processes, Materials and Manufacturing Processes, Vol. 18, No. 1, pp 1-22
- [17] Luiz A. and Fernandes M.S. (2012), Occurrence of Defects in Laser Beam Welded Al-Cu-Li Sheets with T-joint Configuration, J. Aerosp. Technol. Manag., Vol. 4, No. 4, pp 421-429
- [18] Srivatsan T.S. and Sudarshan T.S. (1991), Welding of Lightweight Aluminum-Lithium Alloys, Welding Research Supplement, pp173-186
- [19] IAWAS proposal
- [20] Ion J.C. (2000), Laser beam welding of wrought aluminium alloys, Science and Technology of Welding and Joining, Vol. 5, No. 5
- [21] ROBERTO J. RIOJA and JOHN LIU, The Evolution of Al-Li Base Products for Aerospace and Space Applications, The Minerals, Metals & Materials Society and ASM International 2012, DOI: 10.1007/s11661-012-1155-z
- [22] Alexopoulos N.D., Gialos A.A., Zeimpekis V., Velonaki Z., Kashaev N., Riekehr S. and Karanika A. (2016), Laser beam welded structures for a regional aircraft: weight, cost and carbon footprint savings, Journal of Manufacturing Systems, Vol. 39, pp. 38-52
- [23] A. G. Malikov & A. M. Orishich, Laser welding of the high-strength Al-Cu-Li alloy, # Springer-Verlag London Ltd. 2017
- [24] M. Pacchione, J. Telgkamp; Challenges of the metallic fuselage; <https://fr.scribd.com/document/259935731/195-PDF>
- [25] Thomas Dorin, Mahendra Ramajayam, Justin Lamb and Timothy Langan, Effect of Sc and Zr additions on the microstructure/strength of Al-Cu binary alloys, Materials Science & Engineering A, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2017.09.032>
- [26] G. Madhusudhan Reddy and Amol A. Gokhale; Welding Aspects of AluminumLithium Alloys; Defence Metallurgical Research Laboratory, Hyderabad, India
- [27] Sindo Kou; WELDING METALLURGY, SECOND EDITION